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EVALUATION OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES OF REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF THEIR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The article is devoted to the innovative development of Russian regions, which plays a key role in ensuring economic sustainability and increasing competitiveness in the context of globalization and rapid changes associated with the digitalization of production processes. The article examines the impact of innovation on the socio-economic growth of regions, approaches to assessing the effectiveness of their innovative activities and determining the level of innovative activity. The article focuses on the difficulties associated with the implementation of innovative activities in the regions: limited financial resources, insufficient coordination between scientific institutions and businesses, uneven distribution of digital technologies, and insufficient development of digital infrastructure. Obviously, these challenges require the development of new methods for assessing and stimulating innovative activity designed to overcome existing barriers.

For a more comprehensive assessment of the innovation potential and ongoing innovation activities of regions, proposals have been developed to determine groups of indicators and factors for such an assessment, which include not only traditional economic indicators, but also social, infrastructural and technological indicators. Three groups of indicators of the level of innovation activity have been formed: financial support for innovation, the state of the innovation environment and infrastructure, and the effectiveness of innovation activity.

The proposed indicators and factors allow for more accurate consideration of regional characteristics in the process of forming regional infrastructure. The use of an integrated approach will allow regions to optimally distribute resources, improve interaction between scientific institutions and businesses, and adapt to changes in the global economy. Innovative development against the backdrop of digitalization of the economy based on knowledge and improving personnel competencies plays a key role in ensuring economic sustainability and increasing competitiveness.

Keywords: innovative activity, innovative potential, innovative process, innovative development, innovative infrastructure, innovative activity model, indicators and factors of innovative activity efficiency.

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